

```

QUICK CLUSTER Tf2 EG CpG1 AY1 Est
/MISSING=LISTWISE
/CRITERIA=CLUSTER(2) MXITER(10) CONVERGE(0)
/METHOD=KMEANS(NOUPDATE)
/PRINT ID(DATE) INITIAL ANOVA CLUSTER DISTAN.

```

Quick Cluster

Notes

Output Created		23-JUL-2021 12:56:23
Comments		
Input	Data	/Users/sureshnair/Desktop/Restriction_Assay/data file.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	12
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on cases with no missing values for any clustering variable used.
Syntax		QUICK CLUSTER Tf2 EG CpG1 AY1 Est /MISSING=LISTWISE /CRITERIA=CLUSTER(2) MXITER(10) CONVERGE(0) /METHOD=KMEANS(NOUPDATE) /PRINT ID(DATE) INITIAL ANOVA CLUSTER DISTAN.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.01
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.00
	Workspace Required	936 bytes

Initial Cluster Centers

	Cluster	
	1	2
Transposon	2.5	5.9
Endoglucanase	15.0	55.1
CYP6ER1	35.4	25.5
CYP6AY1	45.40	21.29
Carboxyesterase	1.2	49.9

Iteration History^a

Iteration	Change in Cluster Centers	
	1	2
1	16.766	21.572
2	.000	.000

a. Convergence achieved due to no or small change in cluster centers. The maximum absolute coordinate change for any center is .000. The current iteration is 2. The minimum distance between initial centers is 68.360.

Cluster Membership

Case Number	MMM, YEAR	Cluster	Distance
1	JUN 2017	1	18.663
2	JUN 2017	2	19.434
3	JUN 2018	2	8.294
4	JUN 2018	2	21.572
5	AUG 2017	1	15.167
6	AUG 2017	1	15.195
7	AUG 2018	2	20.644
8	AUG 2018	2	16.143
9	NOV 2017	1	16.766
10	NOV 2017	1	11.915
11	NOV 2018	2	28.183
12	NOV 2018	2	37.804

Final Cluster Centers

	Cluster	
	1	2
Transposon	6.1	13.3
Endoglucanase	21.5	44.1
CYP6ER1	35.5	33.8
CYP6AY1	37.96	21.86
Carboxyesterase	14.3	35.1

**Distances between Final
Cluster Centers**

Cluster	1	2
1		35.488
2	35.488	

ANOVA

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	df		
Transposon	151.801	1	77.077	10	1.969	.191
Endoglucanase	1488.361	1	163.490	10	9.104	.013
CYP6ER1	7.690	1	62.454	10	.123	.733
CYP6AY1	756.673	1	58.299	10	12.979	.005
Carboxyesterase	1268.705	1	144.113	10	8.804	.014

The F tests should be used only for descriptive purposes because the clusters have been chosen to maximize the differences among cases in different clusters. The observed significance levels are not corrected for this and thus cannot be interpreted as tests of the hypothesis that the cluster means are equal.

**Number of Cases in each
Cluster**

Cluster	1	5.000
	2	7.000
Valid		12.000
Missing		.000

```
QUICK CLUSTER Tf2 EG CpG1 AY1 Est
/MISSING=LISTWISE
/CRITERIA=CLUSTER(3) MXITER(10) CONVERGE(0)
/METHOD=KMEANS(NOUPDATE)
/PRINT ID(DATE) INITIAL ANOVA CLUSTER DISTAN.
```

Quick Cluster